

A STUDY ON THE RELATION BETWEEN THE INTERNAL STRESSES AND THE EXTERNAL LOADING RESPONSE IN Al/SiC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

By carrying out mechanical tests within a neutron diffractometer the mean internal strains and the external loading response were simultaneously monitored for two different Al/SiC composites throughout their elastic and plastic deformation. The data obtained are analysed in terms of an Eshelby based model. The results testify to the importance of relaxation and plastic flow, not only at high loads and large plastic strains, but over the entire loading cycle. Furthermore, it is proposed that the neutron diffraction technique is sensitive to differences in relaxation about inclusions of different shapes, but that when this occurs care is required in the analysis of the data.

INTRODUCTION

The continual drive to improve the mechanical properties of short fibre metal matrix composites (SFMMCs) has emphasised the need to understand the development of internal stresses in the constituent phases. The usefulness of neutron diffraction techniques for the measurement of internal strains in SFMMCs has already been demonstrated¹. Thus, with the aim of determining the load transfer changes prior and subsequent to the onset of yielding, a loading rig has been designed to fit within a neutron diffractometer². This has enabled a correlation of mechanical test data with the way lattice strains develop upon monotonic loading and we describe here the results of two experiments on composites containing 5 and 10 vol % of short SiC fibres. An Eshelby based model which takes into account the very different elastic properties of the two phases, as well as the elastic/plastic response of the matrix, has been used to interpret the results. This was done both in order to calculate the associated internal stresses from the measured lattice strains, and to relate these to the extension of the composite and the load applied. While the comparison of the measured elastic strains of the two components of the system during the early stages of deformation lends confidence in both the experimental data and in the method of interpretation we have used, this same comparison indicates that once relaxation becomes grossly heterogeneous the approach as a whole needs development.

MATERIALS AND THE EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Two Al/SiC SFMMCs containing 5 and 10 vol % SiC were fabricated at Risø by a powder metallurgy route comprising blending, cold compaction, hot pressing and hot extrusion. The aluminium matrices were free of complicating precipitates except for a 0.8% dispersion of alumina particles caused by the presence of oxide on the surface of the 4 µm sized original aluminium powder (major impurity 0.26% Fe). The whiskers (Tokai whiskers) were predominantly cubic having a [111] growth direction. In both the composites the volume-averaged aspect ratio of the whiskers was about 5 and the whiskers were moderately well aligned with the extrusion direction³. The tensile specimens were cut parallel to the extrusion direction with 50 mm gauge lengths and 4.5 mm gauge diameters. The specimens were annealed at 500°C for 8 hours and slow-cooled before testing in order to remove possible machining-induced stresses.

Because our primary interest is in the distribution of the applied load between the phases of the composite sample, the mechanical testing rig was oriented with respect to the diffractometer so as to allow the measurement of lattice strains parallel to the loading direction. In order to limit the effect of creep during the measurement time, a position sensitive detector (PSD) was used to record complete Bragg peaks in place of a conventional detector which must be scanned step-wise through a range of 2θ . Fortunately, at a wavelength of 3 Å, the Al {111} and SiC {111} peaks are only 6° apart (2θ) so that it is possible to measure them simultaneously using the PSD. The PSD was calibrated to account for variations in the detector efficiency along its length. With an

analysing volume taken from the central 10 mm of the tensile specimen it was found that counting times of 7 and 5 minutes were necessary for the 5 and 10 vol % SiC specimens to achieve peak heights of 6000 (Al) and 500 (SiC), and 3000 (Al) and 600 (SiC) counts respectively for the two composites. The diffraction peaks were fitted to Gaussian functions from which the lattice strain changes could, for symmetric peaks ($\text{FWHM} = 0.9^\circ$), be determined to high accuracy ($0.005^\circ \approx \pm 40 \times 10^{-6}$ strain).

RESULTS

The lattice strain and strain gauge response to monotonic loading of the 5 and the 10 vol % SiC composites were measured and the results are summarised in figs. 1 and 2. The lattice strains are given relative to the thermally stressed state.

Fig.1: a) The Al and SiC lattice strain response for the 5% SiC composite derived using a Gaussian fit to $\{111\}$ diffraction peak profiles, and b) the corresponding composite extension. The arrows indicate the observed unloading response and the diagonal lines in b) indicate the extent of specimen creep during peak measurement.

Fig.2: a) The Al and SiC lattice strain response for the 10% SiC composite derived using a Gaussian fit to $\{111\}$ diffraction peak profiles, and b) the corresponding composite extension. The arrows indicate the observed unloading response and the diagonal lines in b) indicate the extent of specimen creep during peak measurement.

Thermal strains of -1000×10^{-6} (SiC) and 300×10^{-6} (Al) have been reported⁴ previously for a similarly treated 5 vol % SiC composite although with a slightly different matrix. The thermal stresses associated with these strains are 30 MPa (Al) and -500 MPa (SiC) and are equivalent to those which might arise from a temperature drop of 100°C ⁴.

In both figures the inelastic transfer of load from the matrix to the fibre that takes place once plastic flow has begun is evidenced by the onset of non-linear behaviour. Furthermore, this redistribution of the applied load is initiated at very low loads, especially for the 10 vol % composite. In order to understand these results quantitatively we now need to model both the processes which are occurring and how the elastic strains are thereby affected.

MODELLING THE MEAN STRAIN CHANGES DURING LOADING

We have adopted an Eshelby based approach⁵ to model the mechanical behaviour of short fibre composites. Defining the average matrix stress $\bar{\sigma}_M$ as the volume-averaged stress in the matrix, and the mean matrix stress $\langle \sigma \rangle_M$ as the averaged disturbance to the applied stress in the matrix ($\sigma^A + \langle \sigma \rangle_M = \bar{\sigma}_M$), then the balance of internal stress between the matrix and the inclusions can be expressed in matrix notation:

$$(1-f) \langle \sigma \rangle_M + f \langle \sigma \rangle_I = 0 \quad \text{or equivalently} \quad (1-f) \bar{\sigma}_M + f \bar{\sigma}_I = \sigma^A$$

The model predicts⁵ that the mean matrix stress is proportional both to the applied load and to the shape mismatch between the matrix and the inclusions which is itself made up of a plastic term and a thermal mismatch term. Neglecting the latter, as we can given linear superposition and the fact that the measured strains were taken relative to the thermally stressed state⁴, the strain mismatch e^{T*} can be written:

$$e^{T*} = -e^P = e^P (1/2, 1/2, -1, 0, 0, 0)$$

where e^P is the plastic distortion of the matrix along the z-axis which, because of the restraining effect of the inclusions, is not the same as the inelastic extension of the composite. The total extension of the composite relative to the unloaded state can be expressed in terms of the inclusion/matrix mismatch (e^T) needed to set up exactly the same internal stress field within a composite which is homogeneous in elastic constants⁵:

$$\bar{e}_{comp} = e^A + e^P + f e^T$$

The shape of the lattice strain curves of figs. 1 and 2 show that the rate at which the matrix can load elastically as the applied load is increased soon begins to decline. Naturally, if the composite is to maintain the load the fall in the rate of loading of the matrix must be accompanied by an increase in the rate of loading of the whiskers. This redistribution of the load is associated with an increasing misfit between the two phases. We have calculated the misfit (e^{T*}) required to give the observed lattice strains within the Al. This in turn, because of the implicit balance of internal stress, fixes the elastic strain to be expected in the SiC. It would seem from fig. 3 that whilst the model is in excellent agreement with the observed strains during the early stages of loading, it is not applicable at high loads.

DISCUSSION

The elastic behaviours of the two composites are well predicted by the Eshelby model. The agreement between the observed strains and the model points to the onset of plasticity at loads as small as $1/4$ (50 MPa) and $1/10$ (20 MPa) of the UTS of the 5 and 10 vol % SiC composites respectively. This is presumably the result of the tensile thermal residual stresses within the matrix. That more extensive microplasticity occurred for the 10% SiC composite compared with the 5% is also evidenced by the earlier crossover of the Al and SiC strains and by the composite extensions of figs. 1b and 2b. Subsequent to yielding the Al and SiC lattice strains are well predicted by an increase in the plastic misfit approximately in proportion to the inelastic extensions of figs 1b and 2b. Furthermore, upon unloading, the gradients of the elastic return curves are also in agreement with the model.

On increasing the load above 150 MPa and 110 MPa for the 5 and 10 vol % SiC composites respectively, the data as presented are no longer physically interpretable. The SiC strains appear to increase at a rate that, in view of the necessary balance of internal stress, is inconsistent with the Al strains and the applied load. In this loading regime, the composite extension increases dramatically (figs 1b,2b), but the increase in plastic misfit would be expected to be limited by relaxation so as to reduce the very rapid build up of stress in and around the whiskers

Fig.3: An Eshelby based fit superimposed upon the experimentally derived lattice strains for the a) 5% and b) 10% SiC composites. The arrows indicate the predicted unloading response.

that would otherwise occur. For the SiC strains shown in figs. 1a and 2a to be correct the load transfer to the fibres arising from unrelaxed plastic flow would have had to have been so effective that the Al strains should then decrease with increasing load. The observed Al strains are inconsistent with this latter hypothesis, and it seems more likely that instead the SiC strains have been determined incorrectly in some way. A clue to a possible explanation for the inconsistency of the lattice strain data is suggested by the plot of the variation in the FWHM of the diffraction peaks with applied load shown in figure 4. Beyond the loading region at which the strain data diverge from the stress balance predictions the width of the SiC peak begins to increase dramatically. Of course some broadening is to be expected upon increasing the load as local variations in the stress become more marked. However, since the model does not predict any local variation in the strain within ellipsoidal inclusions, such fluctuations would be expected to be greater in the matrix than in the reinforcement. Consequently, the fact that it is only the SiC peak which is severely affected suggests that the broadening arises from different mean strains in

Fig.4: Plot of the variation in Al and SiC full width half maximums (FWHMs) with loading for the 5% SiC composite. The arrows indicate the unloading and reloading response.

different whiskers rather than as a result of local fluctuations about the uniform mean strain. For broadening of whatever origin to explain the apparent imbalance of internal stress it must be asymmetric. Unfortunately, the counting time was insufficient to allow the quantification of the slight asymmetry which was apparent[†]. However, a similar but even more dramatic change in peak width (SiC ~80% increase: ~Al 5% increase in FWHM) was observed in a tensile testing experiment on the 10 vol % SiC composite carried out at -100°C. As at room temperature, peak broadening started near the load at which the strain data diverged from the stress balance predictions. The diffraction peaks now show a more pronounced variation in the SiC peak shape during straining which resembles the lesser changes that occurred during the room temperature tests. In figure 5, six peaks are superposed; these were recorded at applied loads of 0, 150, 210, 230, 260 and 276 MPa and typify the changes that took place throughout the whole series. From figure 5 it can be seen that only minor changes in the width and no noticeable asymmetry of the peaks develops during the early stages of loading. Sometime after plastic flow began, but before the elastic matrix strains saturated, the SiC peak width can be seen to increase through the emergence of a small secondary peak at a strain of approximately 10×10^{-3} (= 1% c.f. average SiC breaking strain ~3%⁶). As the load is further increased, the average whisker strain increases as much by the relative increase in the size of this high strain peak as by the tensile shift of the original peak, so that at the termination point of the experiment the two peaks are almost of the same size. A similar description of the peak changes occurring during the room temperature tests can also be made, though less convincingly because the secondary peak is smaller and thus less distinct.

Fig.5: Six SiC diffraction peak profiles for the cold 10%SiC/Al experiment recorded at applied loads of 0 (1), 150 (2), 210 (3), 230 (4), 260 (5) and 276 (6) MPa.

Clearly it is not satisfactory to use the shift in peak position of a Gaussian to evaluate average lattice strains when the peaks become asymmetric. The broadening of the SiC peak, combined with the fact that the Al peak width barely changes, indicates that the error of interpretation implicit in the lack of stress balance in figs.1a and 2a lies in the evaluation of the SiC lattice strain rather than in any miscalibration of the detector, bending of the sample or some inherent fault in the experimental set-up. This suggests that the SiC peak shape is sensitive to wholesale differences in average strain in an increasingly significant fraction of the whiskers. The divergence of the Gaussian fitted data from the predicted response occurs near the beginning of the knee in the composite extension curves. The associated increase in plastic flow means that the concomitant rise in whisker stress will be limited increasingly by relaxation. Following this argument and given the large spread in whisker aspect ratios present, it seems probable that the asymmetry is the result of the activation of a relaxation mechanism which, initially at least, is only available to a minority of the whiskers. There are a number of mechanisms by which relaxation could occur: for example, voiding, whisker fracture, and diffusional and plastic relaxation. With the limited data available it is difficult to discriminate between them; the increase in peak asymmetry on lowering the temperature might be taken as evidence against a diffusional mechanism, whilst other evidence⁷

[†] though more sensitive to changes in peak profile, X-ray techniques are not really suitable for the investigation of bulk strains throughout a loading experiment.

suggests that voiding and fracture are not significant at room temperature except at very high strains indeed. A simplistic approach to relaxation would predict a secondary peak below the original peak, however, relaxation processes giving rise to the observed high strain secondary peak can be proposed. Suppose for example, that relaxation occurs by plastic relaxation and that the reinforcement is made up of a mixed population of long, short and equiaxed whiskers. Initially plastic flow will cause a transfer of load to all the fibres causing the peak to shift and broaden, but not to change shape significantly. At some point the longest whiskers will become so highly stressed that the lattice strain becomes limited by the relaxation process and it is this which gives rise to an increasingly apparent secondary high strain peak. At the same time, the other inclusions will have to take up more of the load so that the main peak will shift a little. Eventually the shorter fibres will attain stresses too high to be maintained so that these will also relax, causing the equiaxed whiskers to strain further and the relaxation limited peak at high strain to rise, as is observed experimentally.

CONCLUSIONS

The diffraction peak response of the Al and SiC phases have been monitored in a metal matrix composite throughout monotonic loading. For elastic and limited plastic straining the peaks were symmetric and the derived lattice strains in good agreement with a conventional Eshelby based model of load transfer. Continued plastic flow gave rise to a loss of symmetry of the SiC peak, but *not* to that for the Al. The high strain tailed asymmetry of the SiC peak which develops can be understood on the basis of a relaxation process which involves fibres of higher aspect ratio reaching a limiting elastic strain earlier during loading than the shorter fibres. It is interesting that despite the very different elastic strains retained in the SiC fibres, the Al peak is not broadened significantly. This shows both that the fluctuating stresses which are greatest in the matrix are not responsible for the broadening, and that despite large differences in the average strains in the individual fibres, the average matrix strain throughout the matrix is uniform. We must also note that when there are changes in peak shape the use of a Gaussian peak fit is no longer appropriate. Instead, an analysis of the asymmetry using improved counting statistics is then required to evaluate the lattice strains.

REFERENCES

1. Withers P.J., Juul Jensen D., Lilholt H. and Stobbs W.M., Proc. ICCM VI/ECCM 2, Ed. Matthews F.L. et al., London, Pub. Elsevier (1987), 2, 255.
2. Lilholt H, Juul Jensen D., Lorentzen T. and Withers P.J., (1989), To be Submitted to Scripta Met.
3. Juul-Jensen D., Lilholt H. and Withers P.J., Mechanical & Physical Behaviour in Metallic & Ceramic Composites Ed. H. Lilholt et al., 9th International Risø Symposium, (1988), p413.
4. Withers P.J., Pedersen O.B, Lilholt H. and Stobbs W.M., (1989), Submitted to Acta Met.
5. Eshelby J.D., In: *Prog. Solid Mech.*, 2, (1961), 89.
6. Petrovic J.J. and Hoover R.C., *J. Mat. Sci.*, 22,(1987),517.
7. Warner T.J., (1988), Private Communication.

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